

A Cross-sector Data Space for Correlating Environmental Risks with Human Health

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Abstract. Data spaces are one of the key technology pillars of the European Strategy for Data, which intends to establish a single market inside the European Union (EU) for the efficient and secure sharing and interchange of data across industries. A data space that could combine and correlate cross-sector knowledge from the healthcare and environmental sectors could play a crucial role in determining the future of healthcare. Given that climate change is the single greatest health threat facing humanity and that health professionals worldwide are already responding to the health harms caused by this developing crisis, such a solution would enable the identification and correlation of environmental influences on human health as well as the extraction of novel biomarkers. However, the difficulties in creating such infrastructure necessitate cutting-edge, multidisciplinary research in numerous fields. This manuscript contributes into providing a visionary approach toward a single-entry point ecosystem to access, share, and trade cross-sector data assets originating from the environmental and healthcare domains through a Cross-sector Data Space (CDS), thereby effectively promoting European technological autonomy in data sharing. This CDS will consider a variety of analytics as ready-to-use solutions to facilitate analysis, prediction, and monitoring of the causality, correlation, reasoning, and practical visualization of real-time environmental settings, as well as to identify the effects of climate change to human health.

Keywords: Data Space, Data Sharing, Climate Risk, Human Health, Environmental Impact, Environmental Risk.

1 Introduction

The European Strategy for Data aims at creating a single market for data to be shared and exchanged across sectors efficiently and securely within the European Union (EU) [1]. Data spaces is one of the main technological building blocks towards this target [2]. During the last years, the development of various data spaces has taken place as part of initiatives like GAIA-X [3], including data spaces in sectors like healthcare, finance, and industry. The latter enable organizations to share data in trusted and interoperable ways, while at the same time realizing mechanisms for data generation, curation, trading, and monetization. Nevertheless, there are many cases

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where data economy stakeholders must simultaneously access, combine, and process with data from multiple ecosystems and different data spaces from various sectors. This is for example the case for applications that need to derive or correlate insights from different, yet related, sectors such as finance and insurance, energy and manufacturing, as well as environment and healthcare. In such cases, state of the art data spaces initiatives fall short, as data spaces from different sectors and thematic areas must be integrated, nested and inter-related. Interconnecting such data spaces is a key enabler for cross-domain use cases. As a prominent example, such inter data space capabilities are required in the healthcare and environment sectors, where several isolated data spaces exist [4], without effective ways for combining correlated knowledge. This combination can play an instrumental role in shaping the future of healthcare, through identifying, anticipating, and factoring environmental influences on human health, while extracting novel biomarkers. However, the challenges of developing such infrastructure require multi-disciplinary, cutting-edge research.

Due to the ongoing climate crisis and its proven impact to human health [5], healthcare providers, environmentalists, regulators, researchers, as well as citizens require more efficient access to cross-domain knowledge, concerning collateral impacts and implications of the environmental domain, and more precisely the impacts of natural hazards (e.g., heatwaves, floods) to human health, with high data availability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability, along with the support of analytical capabilities. A cross-sector data space can facilitate decision making and planning, increasing its involved parties' awareness, along with the fact that the available information on human health (e.g., wearable sensors, social media) and environment (e.g., air and water sensors, micro-satellites) is explosively growing, holding great promise in providing cross-sectoral critical insights. Hence, what is of critical importance is not only to offer siloed markets of healthcare and environmental data to assess these emerging threats, but to realize a cross-sector data space for collecting, storing, processing, discovering, and analyzing data of both sectors (i.e., healthcare and environment), supporting the correlation and the causal inference of their available data, based on Machine/Deep Learning (ML/DL), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven analytical procedures. Despite recent improvements in cutting-edge ML/DL and AI techniques, it is still challenging to clearly identify and correlate the impacts of environmental factors on human health, whereas their effects are not broadly understood and accounted to support effective decision-making. This is because climate-driven health risks are complex, often invisible, and hard to be accurately predicted. Moreover, the identification of causality relationships beyond simple correlations is hardly possible with traditional ML and analytics techniques. Therefore, the need for advanced AI reasoning techniques that put in place all the causes that lead to threatening environmental situations, while also identifying and analyzing the diversity of their factors that affect human health is more than crucial.

What is more, there is a great need for realizing interoperable data spaces [6], by viewing interoperability as the new norm for facilitating mass adoption and scalability, on top of agreed standards, common vocabularies, ontologies, data models, and reference architectures. Therefore, an innovative, robust, and interoperable data space for the entire lifecycle of healthcare and environmental data must be developed. The

data space should aim at secure and efficient AI-based data operations, further supporting explainability, interoperability, sharing, reusing, and trading high-quality and high-value fairly priced data assets (i.e., raw data, analysed data, data services, algorithms, etc.), thus expanding common European data spaces. What is also lacking is proper motivations for data providers to be convinced about the value of their data assets, thus assured of sharing them for additional research and exploitation. Hence, data providers must be encouraged to join in data spaces and must be provided with customized incentives to share and trade more data assets. Moreover, data spaces should be established in a coordinated way, combining technological, functional, and legal processes, adopting legislative measures on data governance and reuse, applying security/privacy-by-design, and assuring compliance to applicable laws (e.g., General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7]).

In this context, the aim of this manuscript is to provide a visionary approach towards a single-entry point ecosystem to access, share, and trade cross-sector data assets deriving from the environmental and healthcare domains, through a Cross-sector Data Space (CDS), effectively contributing to the European technological autonomy in data sharing. This CDS will consider various analytics as ready-to-use data assets, exploiting ML/DL/AI/ Explainable AI (XAI) to facilitate the analysis, prediction, and monitoring of the causality, correlation, reasoning, and pragmatic visualization of real-time environmental settings, identifying human health impacts of environmental hazards, and their reverse correlation. Hence, direct and indirect human health impacts could be measured, creating, extending, explaining, and interlinking domain-specific and domain-agnostic knowledge.

The rest of the manuscript has the following structure. In Section 2, the ambition behind the envisioned CDS is being provided, referring to the emerging need of technological solutions towards addressing the climate impact on human health. Section 3 contains the visionary architecture of the CDS, while Section 4 summarizes the CDS's added value to its stakeholders, concluding with our next plans.

2 Ambition & Related Challenges

2.1 Environmental Impacts on Human Health

The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) highlighted that “2021 was a make-or-break year for climate action, with the window to prevent the worst impacts of climate change closing rapidly” [8]. The modern climate era is mainly characterized by the increase of climate changes, influencing the amount of solar energy that is received in our planet. Planet warming is happening almost ten times faster than the average rate of ice-age-recovery warming, with carbon dioxide produced by human activities exponentially increasing [9]. Currently it is proved that the average surface temperature has risen about 1.18 degrees Celsius since the late 19th century, due to increased carbon dioxide emissions and other human activities [10]. This heat increase was absorbed by the ocean, with the top 100 meters of ocean showing warming of more than 0.33 degrees Celsius since 1969. At the same time, the amount of snow has decreased over the past five decades and the snow is melting earlier, affecting the

overall sea levels. All these phenomena are mostly related to the global warming trend, provoking the “greenhouse effect”. Considering such evidence, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that climate change will cause at least 250.000 additional deaths per year globally between 2030 and 2050, whereas in the EU environmental factors are estimated to account for almost 20% of all deaths [11].

It is already predicted [12] that increased concentrations of greenhouse gases will lead to increased deaths and illnesses from heat and potential decreases deaths from cold, whereas augmented air pollution or chemicals will negatively impact indoor and outdoor air quality, affecting the human respiratory and cardiovascular systems. In this context, it is estimated that higher pollen concentrations and longer pollen seasons will increase allergic sensitization and asthma episodes, decreasing the overall productivity and public health, while extreme events will create health risks due to damage of property, destruction of assets, loss of infrastructure and public services, social and economic impacts, environmental degradation, and other factors. Additionally, biodiversity anomalies or disruption of ecosystems will transfer viruses, bacteria, and protozoa, and higher concentrations of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere will affect food safety and nutrition, disrupt, or slow the distribution of food, and distress mental health. With these emerging challenges, EU is trying to decrease climate change through policies at home and close cooperation with international partners, where based on these it is already met a reduction of gas emissions [13], whereas it expects that emissions will be furtherly reduced by at least 55% by 2030 [14]. Furthermore, by 2050, EU aims to become the world’s first climate-neutral continent and a climate-resilient society [15]. Nevertheless, these are just a few examples of what EU is targeting towards “Living and working in a health-promoting environment”, and therefore a combination of technology, policies, and strategies should be provided towards addressing the climate-change impact on human health.

2.2 Cross-Sector Data Space Challenges

Transparency. Despite the well-structured specifications [16] about data spaces development, including standardizations and rules, there are still very few practical and scalable implementation of data spaces. In healthcare, the creation of a European Health Data Space (EHDS) is one of the priorities of the Commission, while on the other hand, the environmental sector is supported by the Green Deal Data Space along with the European Green Deal priority actions and EU programmes [17] (e.g., Galileo, Copernicus). Nevertheless, these initiatives have a specific sectoral focus and are confined to siloed use cases with limited interoperability, domain-specific authorization methods, and common analytics capabilities, providing partial discoverability and usability, and lacking advanced and trusted AI tools that can turn cross-sector data into insights. Data sharing, and trading schemes are not always considered, while not any cross-sector interlinkings are triggered, even though the environmental aspect is a driving factor for humans’ health [18]. Hence, the vision is to implement cross-sector data spaces’ building blocks, interlinking healthcare and environment, through guidelines, standards, and protocols.

Data Interoperability. The variability of vocabularies refers to generating mismatches (e.g., syntax, logical representation), ontologies (e.g., scope, model coverage, granularity), explications (e.g., paradigm, concept), and terminologies (e.g., synonyms) that lack standardisation initiatives, followed by unstructured legacy data [19]. On top, existing ontologies, vocabularies, models, and data cannot be efficiently accessed or even located, since most of them are not uploaded to trusted repositories, not exploiting data spaces and persistent identifiers (e.g., Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) [20]). Moreover, data can still be found trapped in silos, making it hardly accessible due to lack of single-entry points identity management mechanisms, or uninterpretable due to lack of explainability tools (e.g., XAI) [21]. Scientific complexity may be another data issue, whereas the different data models and policies of the environment and health domains are creating additional barriers in interpreting the extracted interlinking insights, since no interoperable cross-sector standards exist, while the outcomes importance and priorities differ between the two sectors [22]. Hence, the vision is to enable the ingested data interoperability through advanced semantic modelling, representation, and interlinking of cross-sector ontologies and models, applying data cleaning and interoperability standards-based techniques to detect and correct corrupt or inaccurate records and homogenize the collected data, whilst assigning data usage license and provenance information to make the data nature clear.

Data Assessment. Data scientists devote up to 80% of their time managing data before extracting any insights, delaying its assessment, monetization, and further treatment as an asset, while continuity is still a challenge [23]. These create additional data valuation issues, since there is currently no data monetization law, while data collection is highly decentralized, arising legal and social implications [24]. The treatment of data as separate assets is missing, through recognizing its importance, better organizing metadata, integrating data monetization as a business strategy, and encouraging growth, whilst communicating the data value, through market dynamics. Data monetization comes along with data sharing, including the challenges of data organization, copyright and licensing, multi-variety of repositories, lack of time to deposit data, and increased costs of sharing [25]. Balancing the benefits of data access and sharing with the risks, while considering private, national, and public interests may be an option for promoting data sharing. What is also needed is the reinforcement of trust and empowering users to share data and maximize the data re-use value. To this end, the encouragement of data provision via incentive tools is needed, acknowledging data markets limitations, and addressing data ownership uncertainties, intellectual property rights (IPRs) and ownership-like rights [26]. What is required, is a set of tools to value the assets nature, provenance, maturity, implementation/collection way, attributes, production, quality, completeness, application context, potential use cases, and relevant data assets. For efficient assets' assessment suitable data valuation and market dynamics methodologies should be applied to determine growth opportunities and supply/demand factors, whereas an incentives mechanism should encourage data providers to share/trade more data assets.

Reasoning of Climate Change and Human Health. Interpretability and reasoning over both domain-specific and cross-sector knowledge (i.e., healthcare, environment) through AI systems is to ensure AI operations' transparency and accountability to minimize poor decisions [27]. However, this is still performed based on past patterns and correlations, while since environmental conditions evolve, so does the human health, and thus static environments, closed problems, and lack of "predicting" scenarios may lead to cross-sector correlation inefficiencies [28]. With AI systems focusing on singular/limited tasks, relying solely on "training" data, the further usage of deep reasoning tools cannot adjust networks' weights for admissible solutions as the learning process advances. That is why, complex, often invisible, climate-driven health risks, are becoming extremely difficult to be accurately predicted, considering also that causality beyond simple correlations is hardly possible with traditional ML/analytics techniques [29], followed by increased energy inefficiencies. Also, there are missing reasoning techniques for explainable models, maintaining high searching, learning, and causal performance, while most XAI models deal with siloed non-interlinked sectors. In this context, it should be provided analytical capabilities, for large amounts of transactions. Data-based knowledge graphs extracting causal drivers combined with constraint reasoning could identify/quantify the reasons for climate hazards that threaten human health. Multisectoral causal AI analysis could quantify implications of environmental factors to human health, combined with the reasoning results, identifying enduring causal signals. Thus, the web of causes of an event could be identified, providing insights, enhancing trustworthiness and explainability, enabling humans to reason the outcomes of AI models.

3 Visionary Cross-Sector Data Space

3.1 Overall Concept

Considering current needs and challenges, the overall concept of the envisioned Cross-sector Data Space (CDS) ecosystem is to be accessible through a single-entry point, facilitating healthcare groups, environmental groups, regulatory groups, as well as citizens and researchers to securely access, share, trade, and analyze cross-sector data covering the environmental and healthcare domains towards a data economy capable of ensuring digital autonomy. These cross-sector data will concurrently consider various sources and initiatives, existing healthcare data spaces as well as environmental sources and data spaces, and will follow the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) paradigm being efficiently and fairly priced, and able to be traded in a secure and user-friendly way. This CDS ecosystem will offer analytics services to facilitate inter-domain analysis, prediction, quantification, and monitoring of the causality and reasoning of real-time environmental conditions, identifying the human health impacts of environmental hazards due to climate change and their reverse correlation. All these will be both developed and supported by cutting-edge technologies, supporting environmental sustainability, and an attractive, secure, and dynamic data-agile economy.

3.2 Cross-sector Data Space Architecture

The envisioned CDS aims on effectively contributing to the EU technological autonomy in data sharing through its two (2) layers (Fig. 1), as explained below:

Fig. 1. Overview of the Cross-sector Data Space.

Data Catalogue & Data Assets Management Suite. This layer will consist of the components related with the *Data Catalogue*, *Multi-sources Data Collection*, *Data FAIRification*, *Data Assets Monetization & Trading*, and *Data Market Dynamics Analysis*, where each component will have its unique role, as indicated below (Fig. 2):

Fig. 2. Overview of the Data Catalogue & Data Assets Management Suite.

Data Catalogue. The Data Catalogue will deliver FAIR, discoverable, efficient, and fairly priced data assets to its various stakeholders for easily finding, accessing, processing, sharing, trading, and reusing the CDS data assets. It will include assets deriving from individuals, sector-specific target groups, as well as cross-sector and currently isolated data spaces in the healthcare and environmental domains. For each entry in

the data space, additional information will be stored with respect to the data source nature, the use cases in which the data asset has been used, and its purpose within the context of the CDS.

Multi-sources Data Collection. These techniques will collect scattered healthcare and environmental data in one place securely ingesting: (i) Remote sensing data (satellite imagery (e.g., Copernicus [30]), social listening, data from surveillance tools and climate data sources (e.g., NASA Earth Observatory [31]), Sensors data of smart environments, (ii) Citizen science data collected from citizens' electronic devices (e.g., geolocation, demographic, health-related statistics, crowdsourcing, emotional data), (iii) Individuals' raw data/biomarkers (e.g., vital signs from wearable devices), (iv) Existing regulations (e.g., GDPR), and policies (health and climate), and (v) Data assets from external sector-specific data spaces (e.g., DIAS [32], Green Deal [33]).

Data FAIRification. These techniques will offer cross-sector data modelling, cleaning, interoperability, and aggregation for effectively managing/interlinking the collected data and their FAIR delivery. For data heterogeneity, it will be provided semantic representation via a meta-interpretation layer, enabling modelling and annotation of the ingested data with metadata and identifiers, for efficient discovery (Findability, Accessibility). Diverse data cleaning/interoperability standards-based methods (e.g., OpenRefine [34]) will be applied to detect and correct inaccurate records and homogenize the collected data (Interoperability), whilst a cross-sector data aggregation layer will fuse, link, and aggregate all the incoming data. The latter will also assign data usage license and provenance information to make clear how, why and by whom the data has been created/processed (Reusability). This will result to high transparency standards and wider adoption of the data.

Data Assets Monetization & Trading. These services will rely on the combination of the Big Data Value Chain (BDVC) strategies [35] along with Big Data monetization techniques, offering an XAI-driven multi-phased data value assessment mechanism to capture and harvest the value of the CDS data assets over time. It will automatically value the assets nature (e.g., volume, variety, reliability, sensitivity), provenance (e.g., data from vulnerable groups such as cancer survivors related with pollution levels, may have higher cross-sector added value than data deriving from an activity tracking device), maturity (e.g., raw, analyzed), collection/implementation way (e.g., data I/O), data attributes, production pathway (i.e., low to high ease of production), current application context, and potential future data both individual and cross-domain (healthcare and environmental) use cases, concurrently identifying and inventorying relevant data assets, whilst considering existing valuation models (i.e., Data/Insight/Analytics enabled Platform/Multiple industry Platforms-as-a-Service) for better XAI results. On top of the valuable data assets, these services will include an Adaptive Multi-Agent System for fairly implying the data assets' price, focusing on "how" (i.e., what are the best sales conditions to reach the required objectives) instead of "what" (i.e., which price to propose for the data), supporting, also the possibility for a user to price a data asset by herself. A customized incentives mechanism will

also be offered tailored to each population group according to their profile, location, and generic requirements, to encourage data providers to join in the CDS and share/trade more assets. The data consumers will be able to decide on incentives to pay to the data providers, by considering the profit to be made from the collected data. By sharing the consumers' profit with the data provider as incentive, the data provider will get fair prices for providing her data (i.e., data awarding system). This will include a truthful price report mechanism guaranteeing that the data provider takes the optimal profit when she reports honestly her privacy price, while based on this, the consumer can maximize her profit within a potential budget constraint. These will be established via appropriate Service Level Agreement (SLA [36]) auditing among the interacting parties articulating the terms of the monetization and trading agreement, guaranteeing quality, completeness, and the respective provenance guidelines.

Market Dynamics Analysis. These tools will identify the factors that affect the CDS market, and the data monetization models, including the supply, demand, price, and quantity of the offered/traded/shared data assets, also considering what may potentially affect the envisioned business models. Market dynamic tests (e.g., Knowage [37]) will: (i) evaluate overarching market dynamics to determine CDS growth opportunities, (ii) determine the factors affecting the supply and demand of specific assets, and (iii) most properly and fairly assess and value the provided data assets. The toolkit will also identify what is driving the current demand, leading to decisions for growing, shrinking, or leaving the demand flat. Finally, it will focus on the demand drivers and limiters (including relevant macroeconomic indicators impacting this market), by studying fiscal/monetary policies to see the interest rates and prices in similar cross-sector data markets, to observe how stakeholders react to projections about the market's future, and to identify how much the CDS is needed and has the potential to stand out amid competitors. To boost user-friendliness, interactive visualizations will rationalize the market dynamics evolution pathway.

Inter-domain AI Analytics Toolbox. This layer will consist of the components related with the *Environmental Hazards AI Reasoning*, *Health & Emotion AI Analytics*, *Causal Inferences*, and *Pragmatic Visualization Workbench*, where each component will have its unique role, as indicated below (Fig. 3):

Fig. 3. Overview of the Inter-domain AI Analytics Toolbox.

Environmental Hazards AI Reasoning. These services will identify the reasons that led to environmental hazards due to climate change and their effects (e.g., increased

heating levels lead to wildfires, causing air pollution), supporting what-if scenarios prior to analytics, for energy and time efficiency. This will be achieved by training reasoning structures to predict the most logical causes and effects of environmental hazards, by exploiting a data-oriented knowledge graph platform to apply advanced reasoning to the collected data and discover new insights following DRNets [38] and constraint reasoning, understanding why something happened and how current circumstances must change to improve future outcomes. Thus, the cause-and-effect concept will be supported explaining why a hazard happened, extracting non-predictable correlation results, and concluding on how current circumstances must change to improve future outcomes.

Health & Emotion AI Analytics. These services will provide an additional source of information towards interventions for improving the quality of life of individuals, by facilitating the analysis of data towards extracting knowledge (i.e., healthcare biomarkers that factor environmental parameters) regarding their medical/physical and mental health data (i.e., emotions), thus predicting how, when, and in whom a disease will develop, by applying traditional ML (e.g., SciKit Learn Support Vector Machines (SVM)[39]), and DL (e.g., TensorFlow Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) [40]) techniques. Regarding medical/physical health data, data-driven analytics will be applied, for assessing individuals' health status and predicting the onset of a disease based on their living conditions, identifying the reasons behind such disease (e.g., air pollution leads to respiratory episodes, increasing the need for air ionizers, leading to raised heating levels).

Causal Inferences. These services will monitor the evolution of human health by observing causal inferences based on humans' exposure to specific environmental hazards (e.g., wildfires may lead to respiratory episodes since they cause air pollution, which causes respiratory episodes), whereas also identifying the causal inferences between the individuals' daily habits and environmental hazards (e.g., increased usage of air ionizers leads to increased heating levels, which may cause wildfires). Thus, the services will identify how environmental hazards affect human health and how human activities lead to environmental hazards, and thus will discover the causal inference regarding how humans' activities affect their own health. To support causality inferences the services will employ graph AI and XAI techniques (e.g., SHAP [41]) that explain interrelationships across features, combining Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) [42], and Exploratory/Confirmatory Factor Analysis (EFA/CFA) [43], providing causality relationships beyond conventional (naïve) correlations.

Pragmatic Visualization Workbench. This tool will offer a user-friendly visualization workbench that will visualize and assess the analytics results in different ways (e.g., correlation matrixes, histograms), while visualizations can be modified on-the-fly by the users via parameters experimentation. It will leverage advanced graph frameworks (e.g., Neo4J [44]) and libraries (e.g., NetworkX [45]) for graph analysis, inference, and visualization over CDS data and captured results, also enabling pragmatic visualization capabilities for demonstrating the analytical results and their potential impacts

on top of its users' digital twins [46]. Each digital twin, acting as a digital replica of high trustworthiness with realistic behavior, will be constructed following the notion of digital twin data, considering their data gathering, interaction, universality, mining, fusion, iterative optimization, and on-demand usage. The workbench will also prompt the users to draw their own visualization predictions via a trinity visualization capability where: (i) the input data will be portrayed to users, (ii) the users will make their predictions, and (iii) the workbench will annotate the gap between users' prior knowledge and actual predictions.

4 Discussions, Limitations & Next Steps

The envisioned CDS aims to offer a solution for cross-sector data assets trading, monetizing, exchange, and interoperability being supported by mature systems towards technological autonomy in data sharing, by exposing to its stakeholders its entire ecosystem consisting of the layers and components explained in Section 3. These will provide the means to develop a cross-sector data space of realistic scope and size, deployable in real-world applications being AI-oriented, user-centric, transparent, trustworthy, FAIR-based, ethical, and legal compliant, offering a variety of added value. (i) *Cross-sector single sign-on Data Space linking environment and health*: The CDS will be a single-entry point hosting environment, offering to its stakeholders a novel data space for enabling the access, sharing, trading, and exchanging capabilities of data assets belonging on two (2) hardly correlated and interlinked sectors (i.e., environment and healthcare). All the available data assets (i.e., collected data, data models, policies, results of analytics mechanisms, etc.) will flow within Europe and across sectors aiming towards the goal of the common European data spaces (e.g., green deal, health, skills). (ii) *Environmental and healthcare FAIR data management and interoperable delivery*: The Data FAIRification mechanisms will enable the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of the ingested data to all the target groups. It will provide advanced semantic modelling and representation via a meta-interpretation layer, applying diverse data cleaning and interoperability standards-based techniques to detect and correct corrupt or inaccurate records and homogenize the collected data, which in principle rely on diverse data models and policies, whilst assigning data usage license and provenance information to make clear the nature of the data. (iii) *User-centered energy-efficient data assets assessment, monetization, sharing, and trading*: The techniques of AI Data Monetization and Trading will harvest the value of the CDS data assets, by monetizing them, zooming-in to their nature, emphasizing to their CO₂ efficiencies for their value adjustment and CO₂ inefficiencies for carbon-penalties application. For facilitating the assets' assessment, sharing, and trading, market dynamics analysis will be applied and visualized via a "market demand review", to determine growth opportunities, and factors affecting the assets' supply/demand. It will be implied a fairly assets' price, based on their nature, their CO₂ footprint, and the best sales conditions to reach their objectives, supporting their self-pricing. Above all, an incentives mechanism will encourage data providers to join in the CDS and share/trade more assets, via proper

SLAs. (iv) *Novel and pragmatic inter-domain analytical insights*: An analytics toolbox including Environmental Hazards AI Reasoning, Health & Emotion AI Analytics, Causal Inferences, and Pragmatic Visualization Workbench will offer to the stakeholders with analytical capabilities, facilitating explainability, being capable of handling large amounts of transactions. The toolbox will be able to identify/quantify the reasons for environmental hazards that threaten human health (physical, mental, well-being), exploiting the data assets residing on the CDS. Also, the toolbox will quantify the implications of diverse environmental factors to human health combined with the reasoning results, identifying enduring causal signals. Thus, the web of causes of a behavior or event will be identified, providing critical insights and correlation results. For increasing the value/explainability of the results, stakeholders will be delivered a visualization workbench supporting the interactive estimation of multisectoral effects of environmental hazards to human health under various conditions, and their parameterization/application on top of users' digital twins for better decision making, what/if analysis, and interactive understanding.

Our next steps include the realization of the CDS envisioned functionalities based on scenario-driven business and technical requirements, considering limitations such as the difficulties into integrating all the different envisioned functionalities, or calculating the carbon footprint of energy-hungry components and algorithms. These functionalities will be put under functional stress tests in the context of external health-related projects (e.g., CrowdHEALTH [47], InteropEHRate [48]) reflecting the needs of diverse EU countries, while the overall architecture will be continuously adapted. Performance evaluations will be also considered, targeting the functionality, the practicality, and the user-friendliness of the envisioned CDS offerings. The extracted results will be continuously monitored and evaluated, whereas they will be communicated to external stakeholders (healthcare stakeholders, environmental stakeholders, regulatory stakeholders, citizens, and researchers), whose services will be facilitated, while their volunteerism will be enhanced for sharing and providing their data assets via the single-entry point of the CDS.

Acknowledgements. The SmartCHANGE project has received funding from the Horizon Europe R&I programme under the GA No. 101080965.

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